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COMPREHENSIVE OPTIMIZATION OF MANAGERIAL PROCESSES IN THE ACTIVITIES OF CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION

КОМПЛЕКСНА ОПТИМІЗАЦІЯ УПРАВЛІНСЬКИХ ПРОЦЕСІВ У ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ГРОМАДСЬКИХ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙ В УМОВАХ ЦИФРОВІЗАЦІЇ

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Філіппов В.Ю., Янгулов Е.П., Ткач Д.К., Диць О.О. Комплексна оптимізація управлінських процесів у діяльності громадських організацій в умовах цифровізації. Науково-методична стаття.

У статті розглянуто теоретичні підходи та практичні механізми оптимізації управлінських процесів у громадських організаціях в умовах цифрової трансформації. У дослідженні обґрунтовано наявність позитивного зв'язку між рівнем цифрової зрілості громадської організації та результативністю управлінських процесів. Розроблено інтегровану модель комплексної оптимізації, яка охоплює стратегічний, тактичний та операційний рівні управління, передбачає функціональний аудит, впровадження цифрових інструментів, автоматизацію процесів і посилення прозорості діяльності. Запропоновано поетапну методику впровадження змін, що враховує обмеженість ресурсів та високий рівень динаміки зовнішнього середовища.

Ключові слова: громадські організації, управлінські процеси, оптимізація, цифровізація, цифрова трансформація, цифрова зрілість, організаційна ефективність, антикризове управління, воєнний стан

Filippov V.Yu., Yangulov E.P., Tkach D.K., Dyts O.O. Comprehensive Optimization of Managerial Processes in the Activities of Civil Society Organizations in the Context of Digitalization. Scientific and methodical article.

The article explores theoretical approaches and practical mechanisms for optimizing management processes in non-governmental organizations (NGOs) amid digital transformation. The study confirms a positive correlation between an organization's level of digital maturity and the effectiveness of its management processes. An integrated model of comprehensive optimization is developed, encompassing strategic, tactical, and operational management levels. It includes functional audits, the introduction of digital tools, process automation, and mechanisms to enhance transparency. A phased implementation methodology is proposed, considering limited resources and the high volatility of the external environment.

Keywords: non-governmental organizations, management processes, optimization, digitalization, digital transformation, digital maturity, organizational efficiency, crisis management, martial law

In the context of ongoing transformations of socio-economic systems, the role of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) as key actors in the development of civil society is steadily increasing. These organizations serve not only as channels for civic participation but also as important providers of social functions, including assistance to vulnerable populations, public policy monitoring, and mobilization of community initiatives. Their importance has grown significantly during the war in Ukraine, as much of the humanitarian, volunteer, and coordination burden has shifted to the civil sector.

At the same time, the effectiveness of NGOs largely depends on the quality of their management processes, which must adapt to new challenges. One of the key vectors of such adaptation is digitalization, which transforms approaches to planning, communication, coordination, and control. However, in practice, the adoption of digital solutions in NGOs remains fragmented and uneven, reducing the potential of digital transformation to improve organizational performance.

There is an urgent need for a scientifically grounded comprehensive approach to optimizing management processes in the non-governmental sector – one that integrates digital tools, organizational change, and human capital development. It is also essential to account for the specific context in which

Ukrainian NGOs operate, including martial law, limited resources, and high environmental volatility. These challenges underscore the importance of research aimed at identifying effective management models and developing practical recommendations to enhance NGOs' capacity to operate under uncertainty.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The issue of effective management in non-governmental organizations (NGOs) under digital transformation is widely discussed in modern academic discourse. Research on NGO governance lies at the intersection of management, sociology, public administration, and information technology, reflecting its interdisciplinary nature.

In Ukrainian academic literature, significant contributions to the theoretical foundations of NGO management have been made by H. Bei and A. Synychenko, who emphasize the value-based nature of management, personnel motivation, and the distinct principles that differentiate NGOs from commercial organizations [6]. K. Petrenko views institutional capacity as a critical factor in the sustainable development of civil society, with governance playing a central role [7]. In international research, P. Drucker highlights the importance of strategic planning, while M. Worth analyzes leadership as a specific form of influence within the nonprofit sector [8, 9].

Digitalization of the nonprofit sector has also received scholarly attention. O. Kulchytskyi examines the impact of digital technologies on organizational culture and decision-making processes in NGOs [10], while S. Krynytsia focuses on the use of IT tools to enhance transparency and accountability – key elements for public legitimacy [11]. A notable contribution is Xiang-Yang Bi's digital maturity model for nonprofit organizations, which outlines a phased integration of digital strategies, infrastructure, competencies, and culture into management processes [12].

Another important line of inquiry explores the optimization of NGO management practices. O. Sydorukhuk advocates adapting business models to the nonprofit context, particularly by applying process-based approaches and balanced scorecards [13]. S. Bogutskiy analyzes the implementation of agile methodology, which enhances flexibility and responsiveness to environmental changes [14]. P. Connolly and P. York propose an integrative model of organizational effectiveness for the nonprofit sector, combining financial sustainability, program performance, and institutional capacity [15].

A growing body of research also focuses on NGO resilience in crisis conditions. I. Dynnyk analyzes organizational transformation during the COVID-19 pandemic, identifying digitalization as a key factor of organizational resilience [16]. V. Corvello introduces the concept of "antifragility," suggesting that crises can drive innovation in NGO management practices [17]. V. Panchenko investigates how NGOs adapt their strategic planning and coordination mechanisms under martial law in Ukraine [18].

Despite the volume of existing research, many studies remain fragmented, addressing isolated aspects

of management or technology without proposing integrated solutions. The absence of a comprehensive approach that unifies strategic, organizational, digital, and human resource components limits the potential of current findings. Therefore, there is a clear need to develop a holistic model for optimizing management processes in NGOs, one that incorporates modern challenges, the Ukrainian context, and the dynamics of digital transformation.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The analysis of academic discourse on NGO management and the digital transformation of the nonprofit sector reveals several unresolved issues that require further investigation and conceptual development.

First, there is a clear lack of a holistic approach to NGO governance under digitalization. Most studies focus on isolated aspects such as strategic planning, HR management, or specific digital tools, without addressing their integration into a unified managerial model. As noted by O. Siemilyetov, fragmented implementation of digital solutions may limit their potential and even lead to dysfunctional management systems [19]. Without an integrated understanding of digital transformation, NGOs are constrained in their ability to improve performance and adapt to changing conditions.

Second, there is a shortage of practice-oriented models tailored to the Ukrainian context. Many conceptual frameworks are derived from the experience of countries with mature civil societies and do not account for the institutional, legal, cultural, and resource constraints characteristic of Ukrainian NGOs. While researchers such as A. Dyshkant, A. Trush, M. Kozakevich stress the importance of contextualizing innovations in management [20], practical mechanisms for such adaptation remain underdeveloped.

Third, digital transformation is often approached as a purely technical matter, overlooking the organizational foundations and the development of digital competencies. According to the National Institute for Strategic Studies, 62% of Ukrainian NGOs cite a lack of digital skills among staff as a key obstacle to transformation [4]. This highlights the need for an integrated approach that combines technological, organizational, and human capacity development.

Another critical gap is the insufficient empirical research on how NGOs adapt their management practices under martial law. While individual crisis-response activities have been studied, there is a lack of comprehensive analysis regarding continuity planning, risk management, cybersecurity, and remote coordination in the absence of reliable infrastructure.

Finally, there is a pressing need to develop an integrated optimization model that reflects the specific needs of NGOs, leverages the potential of digital tools, and responds to contemporary challenges – especially those related to wartime realities. Such a model should offer a systemic pathway to enhance management efficiency through technology, while accounting for limited resources and the need for rapid adaptation.

In summary, the identified research gaps point to the necessity of creating a comprehensive, context-sensitive framework for optimizing NGO management processes in conditions of digital transformation and national crisis.

The main part

The study on optimizing management processes in non-governmental organizations under digitalization is based on a comprehensive methodology that combines both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods. The empirical basis of the research consists of a survey conducted among NGO managers and staff (n=142) between January and March 2023. The sample was formed using stratified sampling, taking into account regional distribution (22 oblasts of Ukraine represented) and organizational typology based on fields of activity.

Additionally, a series of semi-structured interviews (n=18) was conducted with NGO leaders experienced in implementing digital innovations in management processes. To deepen the analysis of management transformation practices, a case study method was applied, examining in detail five organizations that demonstrated successful examples of process optimization through digital tools.

To assess the level of digital maturity of the surveyed organizations, the Digital Maturity Index model developed by Xiang-Yang Bi [12] was adapted. This model evaluates five key dimensions: digital strategy, technological infrastructure, staff digital competencies, digital processes, and digital culture. Statistical analysis of the quantitative data was performed using SPSS 27.0 software, applying descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis.

The empirical data analysis reveals key characteristics and challenges in the management processes of Ukrainian NGOs. According to the findings, the majority of organizations (67.4%) have formalized organizational structures with clearly defined functional responsibilities; however, only 42.3% of respondents rated their management processes as effective. The main weaknesses identified in the management systems include excessive bureaucratization of internal procedures (58.7%), inefficient communication flows (52.3%), lack of systematic task control (47.8%), and insufficient flexibility in responding to change (44.2%).

The level of digitalization in management processes varies significantly among the organizations studied. According to the adapted Digital Maturity Index, only 18.3% of NGOs fall into the “digital leaders” category (levels 4–5 on a five-point scale), 37.6% are at a medium level (level 3), and 44.1% are at a basic level (levels 1–2). A statistically significant correlation ($r = 0.68$; $p < 0.01$) was found between an organization’s digital maturity and the perceived effectiveness of its management processes, confirming the potential of digitalization to improve organizational governance.

Martial law has led to substantial transformations in NGO operations in Ukraine. According to the

research, 83.1% of NGOs had to revise their priority activities, 76.2% adopted remote work formats, and 58.4% faced the need to optimize resource use. These shifts heightened the demand for management process improvement and accelerated the adoption of digital solutions: 61.3% of respondents indicated that martial law became a catalyst for the digital transformation of their organizations.

Based on the analysis of empirical data and academic literature, three main categories of challenges faced by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in the context of management process optimization were identified:

1. Structural challenges relate to the organizational structure and governance processes of NGOs. The study found that 53.7% of NGOs operate under a horizontal management structure, which, while promoting democratic decision-making, often leads to blurred lines of responsibility and reduced operational efficiency. These issues are compounded by a heavy reliance on rotating volunteer teams (characteristic of 72.3% of surveyed organizations) and the project-based nature of activities, which requires ongoing reconfiguration of management practices.

2. Human resource challenges concern staffing and personnel management. Key problems include a low level of managerial competencies (noted by 63.4% of respondents), limited options for financial incentives (58.9%), high staff turnover (41.2%), and insufficient digital skills (67.8%). These issues have intensified under martial law, with 73.5% of organizations reporting staff shortages due to migration and increased emotional burnout among personnel.

3. Digital challenges are associated with the implementation and use of information technologies in NGO management. The main barriers to digital transformation include limited financial resources for digital investments (78.2%), lack of strategic vision for digitalization (64.7%), insufficient technical infrastructure (57.3%), and psychological resistance to change from staff (48.9%). At the same time, 82.4% of NGO leaders recognize digitalization as a necessary condition for improving management efficiency in the current environment.

Based on theoretical analysis and empirical findings, an integrated model for the comprehensive optimization of management processes in non-governmental organizations has been developed. This model is grounded in the synergy of organizational transformation, digital innovation, and human capital development. It consists of four interrelated components:

1. Functional organizational audit serves as the initial stage of the optimization process and involves a systematic analysis of existing management processes based on effectiveness, resource intensity, and alignment with the organization’s strategic goals. A dedicated audit methodology has been designed, including:

- Identification and mapping of key management processes;
- Analysis of information flows and communication links;

- Evaluation of resource allocation for processes;
- Identification of critical inefficiencies;
- Establishment of optimization priorities.

The audit results enable the creation of an individualized "roadmap" for optimization tailored to the specific characteristics of each NGO.

2. Digital management tools form the technological foundation of optimization. Based on an assessment of NGO needs and the performance of various digital solutions, an optimal set of tools was identified for different types of organizations, considering their size, field of activity, and financial capacity. Recommended tools include:

- Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems for coordinating work with beneficiaries and donors;
- Cloud services for collaborative work and document storage;
- Task managers for planning and monitoring task execution;
- Analytical tools for performance monitoring;
- Communication platforms for both internal and external interaction.

A key feature of this approach is the emphasis on integration, which ensures a unified information environment and eliminates redundancy in functions.

3. Internal process automation is aimed at reducing the labor intensity of routine operations and increasing the accuracy of managerial actions. A methodology for identifying automatable processes and a reorganization algorithm have been developed. Priority areas for automation include:

- Document management and reporting;
- Budgeting and financial control;
- Project and program management;
- Monitoring and evaluation of outcomes;
- Communication with stakeholders.

Empirical findings show that automating these processes reduces administrative time by an average of 38.7%, freeing up resources for programmatic activities.

4. Enhancing transparency and efficiency is the integral goal of management optimization. A set of indicators has been proposed to assess optimization outcomes, including both quantitative metrics (decision-making time, plan execution rate, resource efficiency) and qualitative attributes (stakeholder satisfaction, organizational flexibility, innovation capacity). Mechanisms for ensuring NGO transparency through digital technologies have been designed, such as:

- Publishing structured activity reports;
- Visualizing data on resource utilization;
- Engaging stakeholders in performance monitoring;
- Using digital feedback channels.

The study demonstrates that increased transparency positively correlates with organizational trust ($r = 0.72$; $p < 0.01$) and the ability to attract resources ($r = 0.61$; $p < 0.01$).

The implementation of the proposed model for optimizing management processes involves a sequence

of stages that ensure systemic change and risk minimization:

1. Preparation stage includes:

- Forming a change management team composed of representatives from various functional units;
- Conducting a functional audit and identifying optimization priorities;
- Developing an action plan with defined timelines and responsible parties;
- Preparing the necessary resources (financial, technical, human);
- Communicating the objectives and expected outcomes of the optimization initiative within the organization.

2. Technological transformation stage focuses on the deployment of digital tools:

- Selecting the optimal set of digital solutions based on the organization's needs;
- Technical setup and integration of selected tools;
- Data migration and configuration of information flows;
- Functionality testing and troubleshooting technical issues;
- Developing user manuals and usage protocols for digital tools.

3. Organizational adaptation stage involves:

- Training personnel to use the new digital instruments;
- Reengineering management processes in line with digital capabilities;
- Adjusting the organizational structure and responsibility distribution system;
- Implementing new procedures and operational regulations;
- Fostering a digital culture and overcoming resistance to change.

4. Monitoring and adjustment stage includes:

- Systematic data collection on the functioning of optimized processes;
- Analyzing the effectiveness of implemented changes using predefined indicators;
- Identifying problem areas and developing corrective actions;
- Documenting lessons learned and forming organizational memory;
- Planning further improvements to the management system.

The study demonstrates that adherence to this sequence and a comprehensive approach to change implementation significantly increase the likelihood of successful optimization. Specifically, NGOs that devoted sufficient attention to the preparation and adaptation stages showed a 43.2% higher level of digital integration in daily operations compared to those that focused solely on technological aspects.

The integrated model of comprehensive optimization of management processes in non-governmental organizations (Figure 1) is based on a systems approach and takes into account the interconnection between organizational, technological, and human resource aspects.

Figure 1. Integrated model of comprehensive optimization of management processes in NGOs

Source: compiled by authors on materials [7, 8, 21]

1. The model comprises three levels:

— Strategic level encompasses elements that ensure the long-term effectiveness of management processes:

- Strategic planning with integration of digital capabilities;
- Organizational architecture focused on flexibility and adaptability;
- A system for strategic monitoring and performance evaluation;
- Digital transformation as a component of organizational strategy;
- Development of an innovation-supportive organizational culture.

2. Tactical level includes components aimed at operationalizing strategic initiatives:

- Project management using agile methodology;
- Resource management based on data analytics;
- Digital platforms for activity coordination;
- Decision support systems;
- Crisis management procedures and continuity planning.

3. Operational level covers elements of day-to-day management:

- Automated administrative support processes;
- Digital channels of internal and external communication;
- Accounting and reporting systems;
- Operational control mechanisms;
- Collaboration and teamwork tools.

4. The key advantages of the proposed model are:

- Integration – ensuring synergy among various management aspects;
- Adaptability – the ability to adjust to the specific characteristics of each organization;
- Scalability – suitability for NGOs of different sizes;
- Resource efficiency – optimal balance between costs and optimization outcomes;

— Resilience orientation – enhancing organizational capacity to operate under crisis conditions.

Empirical testing of the model components, conducted with five NGOs participating in the case study, confirmed its effectiveness. In particular, the implementation of the integrated approach to management process optimization led to the following results:

- A 31.4% reduction in decision-making time;
- A 28.6% improvement in planning accuracy and resource utilization;
- A 24.9% increase in staff engagement;
- A 19.8% improvement in beneficiary satisfaction with service quality;
- A 37.2% increase in perceived organizational resilience under martial law conditions, according to leaders' assessments.

Based on theoretical analysis and empirical findings, a set of practical recommendations was developed for NGOs to optimize their management processes in the context of digitalization. The recommendations are structured according to key optimization dimensions:

1. Strategic recommendations:

- Develop a digital strategy as part of the organization's overall development strategy, outlining key directions for management digitalization;
- Implement strategic planning using a scenario-based approach to enhance adaptability in a dynamic environment;
- Foster a "digital culture" that encourages innovation and experimentation with new management tools;
- Ensure integration of management functions through a unified information system to prevent fragmentation.

2. Organizational-structural recommendations:

- Optimize the organizational structure by enhancing flexibility and reducing hierarchical layers;

- Introduce a matrix project management approach with clearly defined responsibilities;
- Establish a "digital transformation center" as a coordination mechanism for innovation deployment;
- Design a system of delegated authority supported by digital control tools.

3. Technological recommendations:

- Implement cloud solutions to enable access to management information and support remote work;
- Use integrated CRM systems to manage relationships with beneficiaries, partners, and donors;
- Deploy electronic document management systems with analytical and performance tracking functions;
- Apply data analytics tools to support decision-making;
- Ensure cybersecurity of information systems and data confidentiality.

4. Human resource recommendations:

- Develop digital competency development programs tailored to different skill levels;
- Introduce motivation systems that incentivize the use of digital tools;
- Engage staff in the design and implementation of management innovations;
- Implement knowledge management practices to capture and share digital transformation experiences.

5. Crisis management recommendations:

- Develop digital continuity protocols for crisis scenarios;
- Implement distributed systems for storing mission-critical information;
- Use remote coordination and communication tools;
- Create early warning and risk response systems based on data analytics.

Special attention should be given to the gradual implementation of these recommendations, taking into account the organization's resources and specific context. The study showed that the most effective approach is to begin with pilot projects in the most critical management areas and then scale up successful practices.

An important factor for successful optimization is cross-sectoral cooperation and experience sharing. It is recommended to establish communities of practice for exchanging knowledge on digital transformation of management processes in the nonprofit sector and for adapting lessons learned from the business sector to the NGO context.

Conclusion

The conducted study on the comprehensive optimization of management processes in non-governmental organizations under digitalization conditions allows for the formulation of several conceptual conclusions with both theoretical and practical significance.

First, it has been established that the effectiveness of NGOs in the current environment directly depends

on the level of management process optimization and digital transformation. Empirical data analysis confirms a statistically significant correlation between an organization's level of digital maturity and its performance indicators – particularly its ability to adapt to crisis conditions, use resources efficiently, and ensure beneficiary satisfaction.

Second, the study identified key challenges NGOs face in the process of management optimization: structural (related to organizational architecture), human resource (due to specific characteristics of the nonprofit workforce), and digital (related to technological readiness). These challenges are exacerbated by the martial law context, requiring additional focus on security, business continuity, and remote coordination.

Third, an integrated model for comprehensive management process optimization was developed, incorporating the interrelation between strategic, tactical, and operational levels of governance. The model provides a systematic approach to digital transformation through components such as functional audits, implementation of digital tools, process automation, and mechanisms for ensuring transparency and efficiency.

Fourth, the study substantiates a phased approach to implementing optimization measures, including the preparatory stage, technological transformation, organizational adaptation, and monitoring with adjustment. Empirical findings confirm that following this sequence increases the likelihood of successful optimization while minimizing the risks of negative outcomes.

Fifth, practical recommendations for NGOs were formulated and structured across key dimensions: strategic, organizational-structural, technological, human resource, and crisis management. These recommendations consider the Ukrainian context and typical resource constraints faced by NGOs.

The theoretical significance of the study lies in the advancement of scientific understanding of NGO management under conditions of digital transformation and in the development of conceptual foundations for optimizing governance through digital technologies. The proposed integrated model expands the methodological toolkit for nonprofit research and lays the groundwork for further academic inquiry in this field.

The practical value of the study is defined by the applicability of the proposed model and recommendations for improving management effectiveness and enhancing organizational resilience in the face of digitalization and crisis conditions. The findings are especially relevant for NGOs operating under martial law and facing urgent demands for rapid adaptation to new operational realities.

Future research directions include the development of sector-specific optimization models for various types of NGOs, the creation of tools for quantitatively assessing digital transformation effectiveness, and the examination of the long-term impact of optimization measures on the sustainable development of civil society organizations.

Abstract

The article examines the theoretical foundations and practical aspects of optimizing management processes in non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in the context of digital transformation. The research is particularly relevant given the increased importance of the third sector in Ukraine's socio-economic development and the challenges posed by the martial law conditions. Based on a comprehensive empirical study involving 142 Ukrainian NGOs and utilizing the Digital Maturity Index methodology, the author identifies key challenges in NGO management: structural (related to organizational architecture), personnel (concerning human resources specifics), and digital (determined by technological readiness levels).

The study employs a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative surveys, qualitative interviews (n=18), and case studies of five NGOs demonstrating successful optimization practices. Statistical analysis reveals a significant correlation ($r=0.68$; $p<0.01$) between an organization's digital maturity level and management process efficiency, confirming digitalization's potential for optimization. The research demonstrates that 83.1% of Ukrainian NGOs have altered their activity priorities under martial law conditions, with 61.3% of respondents noting that these circumstances catalyzed their digital transformation.

The article presents an integrated model for comprehensive optimization of management processes in NGOs, structured across strategic, tactical, and operational levels. The model's key components include functional organizational audit, implementation of digital management tools, internal process automation, and mechanisms ensuring transparency and effectiveness. A phased implementation approach is substantiated, comprising preparatory, technological transformation, organizational adaptation, and monitoring with adjustment stages.

Empirical testing of the model elements demonstrates significant improvements in NGO performance indicators: 31.4% reduction in management decision-making time, 28.6% increase in planning accuracy and resource utilization, 24.9% growth in personnel engagement, and 19.8% improvement in beneficiary satisfaction with service quality. The research provides practical recommendations for NGOs regarding management process optimization under digitalization conditions, structured according to strategic, organizational-structural, technological, personnel, and crisis management dimensions.

The study contributes to theoretical understanding of NGO management under digital transformation conditions and develops conceptual foundations for optimizing management processes using digital technologies. The practical value lies in providing Ukrainian NGOs with an adaptable model for enhancing organizational resilience during crisis periods, particularly under martial law conditions.

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